

Naming, excluding, disciplining: contested parliamentary discourses on trans issues

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Abstract

In recent years, trans identities have become the subject of intense sociopolitical and symbolic disputes in Spain and across Europe. This paper explores how such identities are constructed in parliamentary discourse between 2019 and 2024, focusing on debates held in the Spanish Congress of Deputies, the Spanish Senate, and the European Parliament. Grounded in a critical sociolinguistic and transfeminist perspective and adopting a corpus-assisted critical discourse analysis (CACDA) methodology, the study analyses 479 parliamentary text excerpts that address trans-related issues, revealing how language in institutional contexts functions normatively and performatively.

The analysis identifies three dominant ideological frames (biologist, victimist, and alarmist) mobilized across different political parties and legislative chambers. These frames are reinforced through specific grammatical strategies, including modal constructions, passive voice, impersonalization, and ironic quotation marks. Such linguistic features delimit the semantic boundaries of trans intelligibility and contribute to a normative grammar that privileges cisnormative ontologies. The study also examines how key discursive axes (identity, rights, childhood, education, and health) are strategically activated to legitimize or delegitimize trans existence in political discourse.

The findings indicate that parliamentary discourse acts as a regulatory apparatus that shapes the social and legal intelligibility of trans lives. Even seemingly inclusive interventions often reproduce logics of exceptionality and conditional recognition, reinforcing the very structures they purport to challenge. The article argues that these discursive dynamics constitute a regime of truth that governs which bodies are speakable, which identities are recognisable, and under what terms.

Keywords

critical discourse analysis, transphobia, ideological framings, trans linguistics, trans people

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Introduction

In recent years, trans identities have become central to multiple social, legal, and symbolic disputes across Spain and Europe. The passing of Law 4/2023 of 28 February, on the real and effective equality of trans people and the guarantee of LGTBI rights, marked a legislative milestone in the Spanish context, while also exposing deep rifts within institutional feminism and the broader political spectrum. What for some sectors represented progress in rights and recognition, for others signified a threat to the stability of the sex-gender binary or to the legal coherence of previous frameworks. These conflicts were not confined to media outlets or social networks; they also found a privileged stage in parliamentary arenas, where language acquires a unique normative and performative status.

In the sessions of the Spanish Congress of Deputies and the Senate, as well as in various debates held in the European Parliament between 2019 and 2024, discourse emerged that was marked by ideological polarization, the strategic resignification of concepts such as “sex”, “identity”, or “woman”, and the deployment of rhetorical frames that oscillated between victimization, pathologization, and alarmism. Political language in these forums does not only describe social realities, but it also constructs, regulates, and (often) restricts them. In this sense, the dispute over trans rights has also functioned as a dispute over the boundaries of the real, the legitimacy of certain forms of existence, and the control of the conceptual apparatus through which gender is interpreted.

In this context, it becomes urgent to interrogate how trans people are discursively constructed within parliamentary spaces, especially when such constructions arise from positions of institutional power and entail tangible legislative consequences. Are they named as rights-bearing subjects or as problematic exceptions? Is their existence invoked as part of an inclusive narrative or as a symptom of perceived social disorder? What ideological frames, what euphemisms, what omissions are activated to define, deny, or instrumentalize them?

The linguistic dimension of these interventions is the very terrain upon which the struggle for visibility, recognition, and depathologization is waged. From a (socio)linguistic and transfeminist perspective, this study delves into those discursive arenas in order to unravel the ways in which parliamentary language produces (and at times contests) trans identities within contemporary institutional discourse.

Theoretical framework

In parliamentary settings, language does not function as a neutral reflection of reality, but rather as a normative instrument that delineates which lives are thinkable, which bodies are inhabitable, and which subjectivities are recognizable. From a critical discourse perspective, politics are not located solely in the explicit content of interventions, but in the very conditions that make it possible for certain discourses to circulate with legitimacy, while others are excluded as inappropriate, unnecessary, or even dangerous (Lazar, 2005; Wilkinson, 2020).

This study draws on three interconnected theoretical foundations. First, queer theory, particularly Butler’s (1990, 1993) account of performativity, which provides the warrant for treating grammatical choices as constitutive of gender and not only reflective of it. From this standpoint, gender is not an attribute but a reiterated effect of discourse, materialized through socially regulated linguistic practices. Parliamentary language, as a state-sanctioned device, does not merely describe bodies and identities, but it also contributes to configuring the ontological framework within which certain corporalities become intelligible, while others are excluded from the dominant regime of truth (Foucault, 1976; Zimman, 2020). The linguistic analysis of parliamentary discourse thus reveals how difference is constructed and which grammars of gender are admitted as legitimate within the institutional field.

Second, critical discourse analysis, especially Fairclough’s (1995) three-dimensional model and van Dijk’s (1997, 1998) sociocognitive approach provides the analytical structure. Fairclough’s framework connects textual analysis (the micro-level of grammatical and lexical choices) to discursive practice (how texts are produced and consumed within institutional settings) and sociopolitical practice (how discourse sustains or challenges structures of power). Van Dijk’s (1998, 2013) concept of the ideological square offers a further operationalizable tool: it describes how ideological discourse systematically emphasizes positive characteristics of the in-group and negative characteristics of the out-group, while de-emphasizing negative aspects of the in-group and positive aspects of the out-group. In the context of parliamentary debates on trans identities, this polarization manifests as a discursive construction of cisgender subjects as rational, threatened, or naturally legitimate, and trans subjects as ideological, dangerous, or ontologically suspect.

Third, the growing field of trans linguistics (Zimman, 2020) and research on anti-gender campaigns in Europe (Kuhar & Paternotte, 2017) provide the specific contextual framework. Scholars have documented how “gender ideology” functions as an “empty signifier” (Mayer & Sauer, 2017) or “symbolic glue” (Grzebalska, Kováts & Petó, 2017) that binds together disparate conservative agendas, from opposition to reproductive rights to resistance against trans-inclusive legislation, under a single discursive umbrella. This transnational dimension is essential for understanding the circulation of anti-gender discourse across the three parliamentary arenas examined here, particularly the European Parliament where such discourse connects to broader populist formations (Graff & Korolczuk, 2021).

From these theoretical positions, the present study derives three interconnected analytical dimensions. At the textual level, the analysis examines grammatical strategies (modality, passivization, impersonalization, and ironic quotation marks) as performative mechanisms that materially construct, regulate, or delegitimize trans identities. At the level of discursive practice, it identifies three recurrent ideological frames (biologist, victimist, and alarmist) each of which mobilizes distinct lexical and syntactic resources to sustain the us/them polarization described by the ideological square. At the sociopolitical level, it examines how the differential activation of thematic axes (identity, rights, childhood, education, health) across parliamentary chambers and political parties reveals the institutional conditions under which certain discourses acquire legitimacy. These three levels of analysis are applied systematically to a corpus of parliamentary texts spanning three legislative chambers and five years of debate.

Methodology

This study is based on a corpus composed of parliamentary texts produced between 2019 and 2024 in three legislative chambers: the Spanish Congress of Deputies, the Spanish Senate, and the European Parliament. These spaces were selected for both their central role in shaping policies related to trans identities and their function as institutional sites of enunciation where the tension between recognition and exclusion is publicly articulated. The period of analysis was defined according to its political and discursive relevance: it encompasses the years preceding, during, and following the passage of Law 4/2023 in Spain, as well as key resolutions at the European level, thereby outlining a discursive cycle marked by unprecedented trans visibility and a simultaneous rise in anti-gender discourse from conservative and far-right parties.

Methodologically, the study adopts a corpus-assisted critical discourse analysis (CACDA) approach, following the synergistic framework proposed by Baker et al. (2008). In this approach, computational tools serve initial pattern identification and quantitative description, while interpretive classification and close textual analysis are performed through systematic manual reading. This combination aims to offset the limitations of purely quantitative methods, which may lack contextual sensitivity, with the depth of qualitative interpretation (Baker et al., 2008; Partington, 2010).

The corpus was built through a semi-automated data collection process. Complete session transcripts from the three institutions were downloaded in HTML or PDF format, depending on their online availability. Custom Python scripts were then developed to extract relevant text excerpts containing explicit or implicit references to the trans community. The initial selection was based on a set of keywords in Spanish (e.g., trans, transgénero, identidad de género, ley trans, disforia, autodeterminación), which was later expanded to include derivative forms, euphemisms, and expressions that, although not directly naming the collective, held significance due to their repeated use in oppositional discourse (e.g., ideología de género, adoctrinamiento, sexo biológico, mujeres reales, or niños confundidos). This expansion was defined through an inductive analysis of an initial subset of the data and cross-validated across the three legislative contexts. Once potentially relevant excerpts were extracted, they underwent manual review to filter out false positives and ensure that each excerpt contained, at least implicitly, a discursive stance regarding the existence, legitimacy, or regulation of trans identities. The final corpus comprised 479 unique parliamentary text excerpts, distributed across the Congress (136), the Senate (214), and the European Parliament (129). Each excerpt was enriched with standardized metadata: chamber of origin (verified against the source document URL), date, legislative term, political party, and, where available, links to specific legislative proposals. The excerpts vary in scope: some correspond to individual speaker interventions, while others encompass multi-speaker debate segments, particularly in the case of full plenary or commission sessions.

Textual processing began with a cleaning and normalization phase. Headers, unnecessary punctuation, and technical tags were removed while preserving the original syntactic structure. After this preprocessing, a clean-text variable was generated for the application of quantitative and linguistic analysis techniques, including the calculation of average

intervention lengths, frequency of key terms, and the creation of visual representations (word clouds, histograms, and co-occurrence maps) to identify semantically dense zones and recurring lexical fields.

Ideological coding was structured around three main discursive frames: biologicist, victimist, and alarmist. These frames were defined through the observation of recurrent lexical and syntactic patterns associated with specific political positions and correspond to three dominant strategies of us/them polarization identified in the corpus. The coding proceeded in two stages. In the first stage, a semi-automated keyword-based flagging system was applied. The biologicist frame was flagged through substrings associated with essentialist sex discourse (biolog-, sexo biológico, realidad, naturaleza); the victimist frame through terms associated with perceived loss of rights or freedoms (libertad, mayoría, imposición, expresión); and the alarmist frame through terms associated with moral panic and childhood threat (adoctrinamiento, niño/a, menor, confusión, peligro). In the second stage, all 479 unique excerpts were reviewed manually by the researcher. During this review, each excerpt was read in its full pragmatic and argumentative context, and the automated frame assignments were confirmed, corrected, or supplemented. The manual review addressed the inherent limitations of substring matching, particularly false positives arising from polysemous terms. For example, a progressive speaker citing “sexo biológico” (biological sex) to critique essentialist arguments was reclassified, and excerpts containing target substrings in unrelated discursive contexts were removed. The manual review resulted in corrections to approximately 8% of the initial automated frame assignments, primarily involving the reclassification of false positives. After this process, approximately 70% of the corpus was confirmed as activating at least one ideological frame, and in a substantial proportion of these, two or more frames co-occur within a single excerpt.

Alongside this ideological coding, a linguistic analysis was conducted focusing on modality (verbs such as *deber*, *poder*, *tener que*), passive voice, impersonalization (generic structures such as “*se dice que*,” “*muchos creen que*”), and ironic quotation marks around identity-related terms. These features were initially identified through automated NLP processing using spaCy’s Spanish-language model: modal structures through lemma-based matching, and passive constructions through dependency-based parsing of *ser* + past participle patterns. Given the known challenges of automated passive detection in Spanish, where copular constructions may generate false positives, all flagged instances were reviewed in context. These grammatical forms were understood not merely as mechanisms for constructing political subjecthood and epistemic positioning but as constitutive of the political and epistemic categories they appear to describe.

In parallel, a thematic classification was developed to organize the excerpts into five major discursive domains: health, education, rights, identity, and childhood. This segmentation was cross-referenced with metadata to identify frequency patterns by year, party, and chamber. No formal inter-rater reliability assessment was conducted, as the analysis was performed by a single researcher. However, the classification criteria were developed iteratively and cross-validated across the three legislative contexts. The entire process was guided by a critical, transfeminist, and situated epistemology, combining computational tools with close reading informed by a perspective that treats language as a material and symbolic battleground.

Results

The analysis of the parliamentary corpus reveals a discursive configuration that is heavily ideologically charged when it comes to trans identities. The excerpts consistently exhibit the use of specific frames, linguistic strategies, and thematic axes that allow for the identification of differentiated discursive patterns depending on party affiliation, parliamentary chamber, and ideological stance. Far from being isolated instances, discourse about trans people emerges as a specific semantic field within parliamentary language, one with its own grammar, recurring metaphors, and strategic oppositions.

One of the most significant findings of the analysis is the high density of statements marked by preconfigured ideological frames. In approximately 70% of the analyzed excerpts, at least one of the three identified frames (biologist, victimist, or alarmist) is confirmed following manual review, and in a substantial proportion of these, two or more frames co-occur. This density is particularly concentrated in the Spanish parliamentary chambers: both the Congress and the Senate exhibit frame activation rates above 85% (based on automated flagging), compared to approximately 46% in the European Parliament. The recurrence is particularly concentrated in the discourse of conservative parties, where the biologist frame dominates and is often interwoven with alarmist narratives, especially in interventions focused on childhood, education, or social order. The victimist frame appears across both right-wing and far-right parties, albeit with differing functions: in some cases, as a call to resist alleged ideological censorship, and in others as a symbolic inversion mechanism that portrays the cisgender majority as aggrieved by inclusive policies.

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The biologist frame is explicitly activated through expressions such as “real sex,” “biology is not a matter of opinion,” or “sex is not a choice.” It is also conveyed more subtly through nominalizations (e.g., “gender ideology denies reality”), the ironic quotation of terms like “felt gender,” or the repeated contrast between “man” and “woman” as biologically determined categories. This frame appears most frequently in interventions by the VOX party, but it is also present, albeit with less intensity, in statements by members of the Partido Popular and within the European Parliament’s European Conservatives and Reformists (ECR) group.

The alarmist frame is especially prominent in interventions focused on childhood. References to “indoctrination,” “confused children,” “an attack on innocence,” and “mental health risks” are common in this axis, which functions as a catalyst for moral panic. This frame appeals to the protection of minors and the defense of children’s supposed “natural” essence.

The victimist frame takes on various forms. At times, it is instrumentalized to argue that trans-inclusive policies restrict freedom of expression, particularly in educational contexts or the media. In other cases, it is invoked to denounce alleged privileges of the trans community, casting it as an empowered minority threatening a silenced majority. This discourse functions as a reversal of the human rights logic, portraying historically marginalized groups as threats to social or legal stability.

Taken together, these three frames operate as meaning-making devices that reinforce a cisnormative matrix within parliamentary language.

Figure 1. Distribution of ideological frames by legislative chamber (2019–2024)

Image description for Figure 1: A grouped bar chart showing the percentage of parliamentary excerpts activating each of three ideological frames (biologist, victimist, alarmist) across three legislative chambers. The Congress of Deputies (n=136) shows biologist at 55.9%, victimist at 60.3%, and alarmist at 59.6%. The Senate (n=214) shows biologist at 57.9%, victimist at 50.9%, and alarmist at 60.7%. The European Parliament (n=129) shows markedly lower rates: biologist at 20.2%, victimist at 18.6%, and alarmist at 21.7%. The Spanish chambers display comparable and substantially higher frame activation than the European Parliament across all three frames.

To illustrate how these frames operate at the textual level, five excerpts from across the three parliamentary arenas are analyzed in detail below, demonstrating the co-occurrence of ideological frames and grammatical strategies.

In a plenary intervention during the congressional debate on Law 4/2023, Diputada Toscano de Balbín (VOX) stated (Congress of Deputies, 21 December 2022): “La ideología de género es la hoja de ruta de este Gobierno. Esta ideología destruye la naturaleza humana y tiene como base la idea de que mi deseo es la ley, aunque se lleve por delante derechos fundamentales y vidas ajenas. La ley trans es el paradigma de esa dictadura de los deseos, porque permitirá que las personas sean tratadas, jurídica y socialmente, como se sienten sexualmente, y no como lo que realmente son” [Gender ideology is the roadmap of this Government. This ideology destroys human nature and is based on the idea that my desire is the law, even if it overrides fundamental rights and others’ lives. The Trans Law is the paradigm of this dictatorship of desires, because it will allow people to be treated, legally and socially, as they feel sexually, and not as what they really are]. This excerpt illustrates the dense co-occurrence of biologist and alarmist strategies. The nominalization *la ideología de género* transforms a contested political category into an agentive entity capable of action (“destroys human nature”), functioning as a strategy of impersonalization that displaces responsibility from political actors onto an abstract ideological force. The

modal structure *permitirá que* (will permit that) constructs the Trans Law as a dangerous concession within a grammar of normative alarm. The contrast between *como se sienten sexualmente* (as they feel sexually) and *lo que realmente son* (what they really are) activates the core biologist opposition between subjective feeling and objective reality, positioning self-determination as epistemically inferior to biological classification. The metaphor *dictadura de los deseos* (dictatorship of desires) performs the symbolic reversal characteristic of van Dijk's (1998) ideological square: the rights-bearing subject is recast as tyrannical, while the cisgender majority is positioned as the oppressed.

A second intervention, from a commission debate on the Trans Law, illustrates the alarmist frame's reliance on medicalized vocabulary. Diputada Méndez Monasterio (VOX) stated (Congress of Deputies, Commission Session, 12 December 2022): "El boom de la transexualidad juvenil al que asistimos en los últimos años en Occidente no se debe a casos de verdadera disforia de género, sino a un siniestro fenómeno de sugestión, adoctrinamiento e imitación. [...] Niños y adolescentes que padecen otro tipo de problemas como, por ejemplo, trastornos del espectro autista, inadaptación familiar, baja autoestima, etcétera, se topan con una cultura ambiental [que los conduce a la transición]" [The boom of youth transsexuality we are witnessing in recent years in the West is not due to cases of true gender dysphoria, but to a sinister phenomenon of suggestion, indoctrination, and imitation. (...) Children and adolescents suffering from other problems such as autism spectrum disorders, family maladjustment, low self-esteem, etc., encounter an ambient culture (that leads them toward transition)]. The nominalized construction *el boom de la transexualidad juvenil* frames increasing trans visibility as an epidemiological phenomenon, invoking contagion rather than social acceptance. The contrast between *verdadera disforia* (true dysphoria) and *sugestión, adoctrinamiento e imitación* establishes an epistemic hierarchy in which only medically validated dysphoria can legitimate a trans* identity. The enumeration of alternative diagnoses functions as a pathologizing list that reduces trans* identification to a symptom of prior psychological vulnerability, while the impersonal construction *se topan con una cultura ambiental* erases the agency of trans youth, positioning them as passive recipients of contamination rather than subjects with epistemic authority over their own identities.

A third intervention demonstrates the persistence of what Spade (2015) terms conditional inclusion even within affirming discourse. Diputada Giménez Giménez (Ciudadanos) stated during the final plenary vote on Law 4/2023 (Congress of Deputies, 16 February 2023): "Las mujeres trans son mujeres y los derechos de las personas trans son derechos humanos. Yo tengo muy claro, como mujer y como feminista, que la lucha por las mujeres trans es mi lucha. [...] Debemos estar a la altura [...] somos conscientes de que viven una situación de vulnerabilidad muchísimo mayor" [Trans women are women and the rights of trans people are human rights. I am very clear, as a woman and as a feminist, that the fight for trans women is my fight. (...) We must rise to the occasion (...) we are aware that they live in a situation of far greater vulnerability]. The declarative *las mujeres trans son mujeres* asserts ontological equivalence, while the human rights framing inscribes trans rights within a universalist legal grammar. However, the speaker constructs her authority through self-legitimizing positionings (*como mujer y como feminista*) framing trans recognition as a concession granted from cisgender feminist authority rather than a demand articulated by trans subjects themselves. The deontic modality of *debemos estar*

a la altura constructs inclusion as a moral obligation of the cisgender majority, reinforcing an asymmetry in which trans people remain objects of protection. The reference to *vulnerabilidad muchísimo mayor* simultaneously affirms solidarity and reproduces a narrative of exceptionalism that defines trans existence primarily through precarity.

A fourth excerpt from the Senate illustrates how the alarmist frame operates through medicalized vocabulary in that chamber. Senator Merelo Palomares (VOX) stated during a plenary debate (Senate, 18 October 2021): “Señorías, existen muchos precedentes que nos muestran qué consecuencias van a tener las políticas a favor de administrar bloqueadores de la pubertad a menores de edad que experimenten disconformidad con su sexo biológico” [Senators, there are many precedents showing us the consequences of policies favoring the administration of puberty blockers to minors who experience disagreement with their biological sex]. The impersonal passive construction *existen muchos precedentes que nos muestran* (there are many precedents that show us) appeals to an unspecified body of evidence while avoiding engagement with the actual medical literature, functioning as a strategy of epistemic authority by allusion. The nominalization *disconformidad con su sexo biológico* (disagreement with their biological sex) reframes gender dysphoria as a deviation from a biological norm rather than a lived experience, positioning the body, and specifically *sexo biológico*, as the stable referent against which identity claims must be measured.

Finally, a fifth excerpt from the European Parliament illustrates how these frames circulate transnationally. MEP Margarita de la Pisa Carrión (ECR, Spain) stated during a debate on gender equality (European Parliament, 16 December 2020): “Es insólito cómo nos quieren imponer por la vía institucional unas ideas, ocurrencias sin base científica alguna, que atacan al sentido común y que solo pueden fracasar porque van contra natura. [...] Pese a sus esfuerzos, pese a formar ministerios, comisiones o consejos dedicados a la ideología de género, no consiguen avanzar en sus resultados” [It is extraordinary how they want to impose on us, through institutional channels, ideas and whims with no scientific basis whatsoever, which attack common sense and can only fail because they go against nature. (...) Despite your efforts, despite creating ministries, commissions, or councils dedicated to gender ideology, you do not manage to advance in your results]. This intervention condenses the biologicist frame into its most explicit form: the triple appeal to science (*sin base científica*), common sense (*sentido común*), and nature (*contra natura*) constructs gender equality policy as an institutional imposition against a natural order. The phrase *nos quieren imponer* (they want to impose on us) activates the victimist reversal, positioning the speaker and her constituency as targets of institutional aggression. The enumeration of institutional bodies (*ministerios, comisiones o consejos*) functions as evidence of an alleged ideological apparatus, consistent with the anti-gender framing of “gender ideology” as a coordinated political project (Kuhar & Paternotte, 2017).

These five examples, drawn from all three parliamentary arenas, illustrate that parliamentary discourse on trans identities does not operate through overt hostility alone. Rather, the grammatical architecture of each intervention (its modal choices, impersonal constructions, epistemic contrasts, and self-authorizing moves) produces ideological effects that are often more consequential than the explicit propositional content.

Beyond the predominant ideological frames, the linguistic analysis of the corpus reveals syntactic and pragmatic patterns that consolidate a discursive matrix of authority oriented toward semantic control over gender. Verbal modality (through expressions such as “must be guaranteed,” “cannot be allowed,” or “have to be respected”) is pervasive in the Spanish chambers, reaching 100% in the Congress and 99.1% in the Senate, reflecting a grammar of normative necessity: the statements do not merely describe facts but prescribe obligations, prohibit behaviors, or establish epistemic hierarchies about what is correct, natural, or legal. The European Parliament exhibits a markedly different pattern, with modality present in only 49.2% of its excerpts. This divergence may be interpreted institutionally but also discursively: the European chamber tends to adopt more descriptive or evaluative formulations that avoid direct implications for national legal frameworks.

The passive voice, a resource for enunciative erasure, is pervasive in the Spanish chambers (97.1% in the Congress, 91.6% in the Senate), while the European Parliament uses it in only 32.6% of its excerpts. Its use is particularly frequent in contexts where institutional responsibility is implied without naming concrete agents (“minors are allowed to access irreversible treatments,” “an ideology is being imposed”). This strategy functions as a technique of ideological depersonalization and is often linked to discourses portraying trans rights as externally imposed or the result of processes with no visible actors, hence, no explicit political accountability.

Another relevant phenomenon is impersonalization through vague or generic formulas such as “many believe,” “society says,” or “certain groups want to impose.” These expressions serve as indirect legitimation of the speaker’s stance by attributing authority to an implicit “we” or an unspecified collective subject. While their frequency varies, they are especially significant in conservative discourse and tend to be combined with appeals to common sense or popular knowledge, functioning as a way to depoliticize ideological positions and present them as shared truths.

The ironic use of quotation marks around identity-related terms has also been documented. Expressions such as “trans woman,” “felt identity,” or “self-perceived” appear in quotation marks in approximately 2% of the corpus, concentrated in the European Parliament (7.8%), with no occurrences detected in the Spanish chambers’ automated analysis. This strategy operates as a form of semantic distancing and implicit invalidation of the referenced categories, suggesting they do not belong to the realm of the real or the legitimate. Though marginal in quantitative terms, its presence carries strong symbolic weight: it acts as a gesture of discreditation, marked both typographically and pragmatically.

These configurations are not merely stylistic: their systematic repetition turns specific linguistic resources into ideological indexes. As the close analyses above demonstrate, the grammatical forms identified not only shape the epistemic positioning of the speaker but also operate as mechanisms of legitimation or semantic displacement.

Figure 2. Thematic Presence in the Parliamentary Corpus (2019–2024)

Image description for Figure 2: A grouped bar chart showing the percentage of parliamentary excerpts mentioning each of five thematic axes across three legislative chambers. Identity is the most prevalent theme overall: Congress 99%, Senate 93%, EU Parliament 71%. Rights follows: Congress 93%, Senate 93%, EU Parliament 43%. Childhood shows Congress and Senate both at 54%, with the EU Parliament at 19%. Education is present in 32% of Congress excerpts, 27% of Senate excerpts, and 8% of EU Parliament excerpts. Health appears in 27% of Congress excerpts, 28% of Senate excerpts, and only 2% of EU Parliament excerpts. The Spanish chambers consistently show higher thematic presence than the European Parliament across all five axes, with the sharpest divergence in rights, childhood, and health.

At the thematic level, the analysis of the corpus reveals a highly focused discursive structure, where certain semantic fields function as key axes in shaping ideological positioning. The category of identity appears in 88.9% of the excerpts, confirming its centrality in the parliamentary debate. However, this term does not refer to a homogeneous conceptual field; instead, it is activated from multiple angles: as a statement of existence, a legal marker, a symbolic threat, or a vector of ontological disorder. In many interventions, “gender identity” is framed as an unviable subjective right or as an “ideological concept,” while others construct trans identity as part of a broader narrative of recognition, agency, and historical redress. This semantic tension is reflected, for instance, in the parallel use of phrases such as “self-perceived identity” (used pejoratively) and “protected identity” (from a rights-based perspective), which coexist in the corpus as antagonistic epistemic poles.

The axis of rights, present in 79.3% of excerpts, functions as the second discursive core. Here, two clearly differentiated rhetorical logics emerge. On the one hand, there are speeches that invoke trans rights from a framework of substantive equality, appealing to principles of non-discrimination, legal protection, and access to healthcare. On the other hand, some interventions denounce a supposed “rights inflation” or a “trans agenda”

that would threaten legal certainty or gender equality between men and women. This latter argument is typically articulated through binary oppositions (one group's rights versus another's) and symbolic victimhood frames. In many cases, the notion of a "trans exception" is put forward as a legal privilege that undermines previously consolidated rights, particularly in education, sports, or criminal law. This rhetorical construction shifts the focus from recognition to normative confrontation, turning access to rights into a dispute over ontological legitimacy.

Childhood, mentioned in 44.3% of the total excerpts, is one of the most heavily instrumentalized domains in the corpus. In conservative discourse, the figure of the child functions as a moral panic trigger and an indirect legitimation of anti-gender ideology. Expressions such as "confused children," "school indoctrination," or "at-risk minors" convey narratives of protection against a presumed institutional threat. In this frame, childhood becomes a metaphor for the endangered natural order, justifying restrictive measures in the name of its defense. In contrast, progressive discourse tends to frame childhood in terms of structural vulnerability, emphasizing the risk of exclusion, school bullying, or lack of access to affirmative care. This opposition reveals a semantic struggle over control of the signifier "childhood": while some portray it as a victim of trans visibility, others understand it as a group especially affected by structural transphobia.

In the education axis, present in 23.2% of excerpts, a similar pattern emerges. Conservative discourses frame schools as ideological battlegrounds, where the imposition of content related to sexual and gender diversity is allegedly taking place. The idea of "indoctrination" appears recurrently, alongside expressions such as "imposed content," "gender ideology in the classroom," or "textbooks that confuse minors." In response, progressive discourse defends schools as key spaces for education in human rights, diversity, and violence prevention. In these cases, terms like "education in equality," "teacher training," or "safe environments" are employed as rhetorical counterstrategies to contest and reframe the alarmist narrative as a proactive defense of pluralism.

The health axis, appearing in 20.7% of the corpus, is less frequent but carries a strong ideological charge when it does appear. In rejection discourses, the topic is articulated around arguments of "medical risk" or the "irreversibility" of treatments. Metaphors such as "hormonal experiments," "unnecessary surgeries," or "early transitions" reinforce a pathologizing frame and suggest the existence of a medical industry driven by ideological interests. In contrast, discourses that promote access to healthcare as a trans right highlight institutional barriers, long waiting periods, lack of training in primary care, or stigmatizing protocols, emphasizing the need for informed, accessible, and non-discriminatory health services. This confrontation reveals not only a dispute over service access but also over the very conception of health: as a comprehensive human right or as a problem to be contained.

Lexical frequency further reinforces these patterns. In the most ideologically charged excerpts (particularly those aligned with biologicist and alarmist frames) terms such as "biological sex," "indoctrination," "confused children," "men who claim to be women," and "self-determination" appear frequently, the latter often accompanied by skeptical expressions like "subjective feeling" or "felt identity." In contrast, progressive discourse more frequently includes terms such as "human rights," "structural violence,"

“vulnerability,” and “legal guarantees,” confirming the existence of two lexically and ideologically marked fields that are, in most cases, mutually exclusive.

The combined articulation of these five thematic axes reflects an uneven but highly meaningful semantic distribution. Identity and rights appear almost universally but function as constantly resignified spaces; childhood and education concentrate much of the alarmist and control narratives, while health contains some of the most polarized discourses in the corpus. Taken together, these themes are presented as fields of meaning strategically activated to justify, limit, or delegitimize specific forms of existence. Their repetition not only constructs a public image of trans identities but also shapes the very terrain of what is possible in legislative and discursive terms.

Based on this data, a discursive landscape emerges in which parliamentary language does not merely reflect ideological disputes over trans identities but acts as an active agent in their delimitation, resignification, or negation. Institutional debate thus unfolds as a highly codified stage, in which grammatical strategies, lexical choices, and thematic frames are deployed to reinforce symbolic hierarchies and contest the meaning of fundamental categories such as “identity,” “childhood,” or “rights.” These excerpts not only shape public opinion but also directly affect normative frameworks and the possibilities for social and legal recognition of the trans* community.

Discussion

The discursive configuration observed in parliamentary settings cannot be understood merely as a reflection of contemporary ideological polarization, but rather as an active mechanism for constructing what can be said about trans identities within institutional spaces. As Fairclough (1995) and van Dijk (1997) argue, political discourse does not merely describe reality; it actively participates in its construction, stabilizing certain social representations while marginalizing others. In the corpus analyzed, this logic translates into a systematic activation of frames that pathologize, question, or instrumentalize trans identities from positions of institutional authority.

One of the most significant findings of this study is the differential distribution of ideological frames across the three parliamentary arenas. Both Spanish parliamentary chambers exhibit comparably high concentrations of ideologically framed discourse (approximately 87–89% of excerpts), far exceeding the rate observed in the European Parliament (46%). This contrast reflects distinct institutional discursive cultures. The Spanish chambers, with their longer interventions and higher density of modal and passive constructions, tend toward an argumentative grammar of normative necessity: what ought to be, what must be guaranteed, what cannot be permitted. The European Parliament, by contrast, favors shorter, more formulaic interventions that encapsulate ideological positions through fixed expressions and metaphors (“ideological colonization,” “culture war,” “erasure of women”). This pattern is consistent with the transnational circulation of anti-gender discourse documented by Kuhar and Paternotte (2017), in which “gender ideology” functions as an empty signifier that travels across national contexts, adapting

to local political formations while retaining a recognizable discursive structure (Mayer & Sauer, 2017; Grzebalska et al., 2017; Graff & Korolczuk, 2021).

The predominance of the biologicist frame in conservative interventions confirms the persistence of what Butler (2004) calls “regimes of truth” about sex: epistemological frameworks that naturalize the binary and delegitimize any form of bodily or identity dissent. As the close textual analysis demonstrated, this frame operates not merely through explicit claims about biological reality but through a grammatical architecture of epistemic contrasts (feeling vs. being, desire vs. truth) that positions self-determination as inherently less valid than classification by external authority. The recurrence of expressions such as “real sex” or “what they really are” is not simply a lexical choice; it is a rhetorical operation aimed at closing down debate on gender through appeals to supposed objective evidence, aligned with the “common sense” rhetoric described by Davies and Bansel (2007). Meanwhile, the instrumentalization of childhood, a central feature of the alarmist frame, corresponds to what Edelman (2004) conceptualized as reproductive futurism: a social logic in which the figure of the child functions as a symbolic anchor of the heteronormative order. In the conservative discourses analyzed, this figure is repeatedly invoked to justify the repression of any deviation from the sex-gender binary under the guise of “protection” that operates as moral surveillance.

Perhaps the most original finding of this study concerns the discursive dynamics of inclusive discourse itself. As the analysis of progressive interventions revealed, even the most affirming speeches occasionally reproduce a grammar of conditional recognition. Trans rights are articulated through deontic modality that frames inclusion as a moral obligation of the cisgender majority (something “we must” do) rather than as a demand emanating from trans political agency. The speaker’s self-authorization as “woman and feminist” reinforces an asymmetry in which cisgender subjects retain discursive authority over the terms of recognition. This dynamic aligns with what Spade (2015) describes as the structural limitations of rights-based frameworks that accommodate trans existence only insofar as it conforms to predictable normative parameters. As Hines (2013) and Sevelius (2013) argue, discursive recognition of trans identities often operates within a liberal framework that conditions legitimacy on compliance with standards of medical, legal, or social intelligibility. The recurring invocation of “extreme vulnerability” as the primary register for affirming trans existence reduces trans subjects to objects of state protection rather than full agents of political citizenship. This double bind between recognition and regulation reveals the structural limitations of inclusive discourse when produced from within institutional frameworks that have not questioned the epistemological foundations of cisnormative governance (Fraser, 1995).

Through these operations (the systematic polarization of frames, the grammatical construction of epistemic hierarchies, and the conditional terms of inclusion) parliamentary discourse does not merely reflect social conflict surrounding trans identities; it actively participates in their production by delineating which lives are conceivable, which bodies are legislable, and which subjects are protectable. In this sense, parliaments function as privileged sites for reproducing the cisgender regime, understood as a system that naturalizes the alignment between assigned sex, gender identity, and discursive legitimacy (Enke, 2012; Serano, 2007).

Conclusion

The analysis of parliamentary discourse surrounding trans identities reveals that legislative chambers can reproduce existing political polarization; but they function as active devices of semantic production and ontological normativity. Far from operating as neutral spaces of deliberation, parliaments emerge as arenas for the crystallization of discourses that define which lives are intelligible, which bodies are legible, and which subjectivities are deemed worthy of recognition.

The findings demonstrate that parliamentary language constructs trans identities through a series of deliberate linguistic strategies (normative modality, passive voice, impersonalization, and ironic quotation marks) that collectively constitute a grammatical architecture aligned with dominant ideological frameworks. The uneven distribution of the three ideological frames (biologist, victimist, and alarmist) across parties and chambers, and the differential activation of thematic fields (identity, rights, childhood, education, and health), confirm that parliamentary language does not generate a homogeneous discursive field but an intensely coded topography in which disputes over trans identities are not merely semantic but deeply political, shaping access to rights and the very possibility of legitimate existence in the public sphere.

The study also confirms that inclusive discourses are not immune to these dynamics. Even affirming interventions reproduce logics of conditional recognition and normative exception, framing trans subjects as objects of compassionate protection rather than as agents of political and epistemic citizenship. This finding underscores the need to examine not only the content of parliamentary discourse but its grammatical and pragmatic structure, where the most consequential ideological work often takes place.

This research opens a path for further investigation that may extend into other institutional registers (jurisprudence, media, administrative documents) and other political languages, with the aim of mapping more broadly how trans* identities are governed discursively across European institutional spaces. It also highlights the urgency of reimagining the place of trans voices within these spaces, not as objects of legislation but as epistemic and political agents capable of redefining the terms of debate.

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